

Improvement Project under heavy field incidence during 1986 kharif and 1987 rabi. Each accession was planted in 10-m² plots with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm, with two replications. Accessions were scored at panicle initiation (PI), when infestation was more than 200 insects/hill.

Eight accessions were found to be highly resistant (score 1) (see table). One was resistant (score 2) and six were moderately resistant (score 3-5). Twelve entries were moderately susceptible (score 5-7) and 15 were highly susceptible (score 7-9).

Almost all the highly resistant entries were derived from crosses involving ARC6650 or Velluthacheera. Resistant entry KAU153-1 was derived from IR1561/PTB33. □

Reaction of differential rice varieties to Manipur biotype of gall midge (GM)

M. P. Singh, Entomology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroisemba, Imphal, Manipur, India

Seven GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason biotypes have been identified, one each in China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Thailand, and three in India (Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, and Ranchi [Bihar]).

We evaluated six differentials (four donors and two derivatives from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad) against the GM population of Iroisemba, Manipur, in 1988 wet season. Thirty-day-old seedlings were planted in 3-m rows per variety at 15-

× 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

Potential donors Eswarakora and Banglei showed low damage; Leuang 152 and Velluthacheera showed higher. Resistant derivative W1263 showed no

damage; Phalguna was susceptible to the local GM population (see table).

These reactions of proven donors and derivatives show that the Manipur GM biotype conforms to the Ranchi GM biotype. □

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1988.

Variety	Donor, derivative	GM incidence (%)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		Infested hills	Silvershoots	Infested hills	Silvershoots
Eswarakora	Donor	5	1	5	1
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	0	0	0	0
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	25	10	75	23
Leuang 152	Donor	15	4	35	10
Velluthacheera	Donor	0	0	50	12
Banglei	Donor	0	0	0	0
TN1	Susceptible check	30	11	75	29

Resistance of wild rices to insect pests

A. Romena, F. Medrano, L. Sunio, E. Camanag, V. Viajante, and R. C. Saxena, Entomology Department, IIRI

We evaluated 185 wild rice accessions--16 species, 4 natural hybrids, and an unknown *Oryza* sp.—against *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, *Marasmia patnalis*, *Rivula atimeta*, *Hydrellia philippina*, and *Nymphula depunctalis*.

Reactions to planthoppers and leafhoppers were tested using the standard seedbox screening test. Reactions against foliage feeders were tested in the greenhouse. Resistance to *S. incertulas* and *N. depunctalis* was

Table 1. Resistance of wild rices to selected species of insect pests. IIRI, 1988.

Insect	Accessions tested (no.)	Resistant	
		no.	%
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 1	185	87	47
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 2	185	66	36
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 3	185	78	42
<i>N. virescens</i>	184	68	37
<i>S. furcifera</i>	185	83	45
<i>S. incertulas</i>	177	41	23
<i>C. medinalis</i>	176	0	0
<i>M. patnalis</i>	176	0	0
<i>R. atimeta</i>	176	0	0
<i>H. philippina</i>	172	13	8
<i>N. depunctalis</i>	172	0	0

evaluated in plants grown in concrete beds. Resistance to *H. philippina* was tested under natural infestation in the field. Plant damage was rated on a 0-9 scale.

Nearly 50% of the accessions were

Table 2. Species of wild rices with multiple resistance to *N. lugens*, *S. furcifera*, *N. virescens*, *S. incertulas*, and *H. philippina*. IIRI, 1988.

Species	IIRI Acc. no.	Origin
<i>O. alta</i>	100111	Surinam
<i>O. australiensis</i>	105165	Australia
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105159	Uganda
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105163	Uganda
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	105144	Brazil
<i>O. latifolia</i>	105142	Costa Rica
<i>O. minuta</i>	105126	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100176	Unknown
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105079	India
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105088	Malaysia
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105119	Philippines
<i>O. punctata</i>	100886	Unknown
<i>O. punctata</i>	105158	Uganda

resistant to *S. furcifera* and *N. lugens* biotypes 1 and 3, more than 35% to biotype 2 and *N. virescens*, 23% to *S. incertulas*, and 8% to *H. philippina* (Table 1). No accession was resistant

to foliage feeders. Seventy-two accessions of 13 wild species, one *O. sativa*/*O. nivara* hybrid, and an unknown *Oryza* sp. were resistant or

moderately resistant to leafhoppers and planthoppers. Thirteen accessions of eight wild species were resistant to multiple pests (Table 2). □

Resistance in different rice genetic lines to rice moth *Sitotroga cerealella* (Oliv.)

M. Irshad, S. Talpur, and W.A. Gillani, National Agricultural Research Centre (NARC), P.O., N.I.H., Islamabad, Pakistan

We tested resistance in various rice lines in Pakistan to rice moth *S. cerealella* (Oliv.), an important storage pest of rice, wheat, and maize.

Rice moth was reared in the laboratory at 28 ± 3 °C and $63 \pm 4\%$ relative humidity. Rice grain also was conditioned at this temperature for a week. About 100 24-h-old eggs of the rice moth were placed on 30 g of conditioned grain. Larvae hatched and were allowed to complete their life cycle. Adult moths started emerging 25 d after infestation.

Infested grain was sieved through No. 20 mesh to separate the frass and food remains, weighed, and loss calculated. Total grains and number of damaged grains were counted and percent damaged grains calculated. The experiment was replicated three times. Moisture content of test lines ranged between 11.1 and 12.6%.

Genetic line 1017-6-B and OP62 showed significantly less grain loss (see table). Highest susceptibility was in line 4439 and Bas 385.

Grain weight was investigated as a possible source of resistance, but no relationship could be detected. Correlations between 1,000-grain weight and weight loss ($r = -0.32$), damaged grains ($r = -0.26$), and number of adults that emerged ($r = -0.31$) were negative. □

Dry weight loss, damaged grains, and number of *S. cerealella* adults that emerged in storage of different rice genetic lines of Pakistan.^a

Genetic line	Crown at ^b	Dry weight loss (%)	Damaged grains (%)	Adults (no.)
1017-6-B	NARC	0.3 a	0.2 a	5 a
OP62	KK	0.7 a	0.8 a	13 ab
OP61	KK	1.0 ab	1.2 bc	24 bc
IET4094	KK	1.2 ab	1.2 bc	27 cd
IR64	KK	2.1 bc	1.5 bcd	38 c-f
TN1	NIAB	2.3 bc	1.7 cde	34 c-f
DM24	NIAB	2.4 bc	1.8 c-f	40 def
OP57	KK	2.7 cd	1.99 c-f	47 efg
DM38	NIAB	2.9 cd	1.9 c-g	49 fg
OP53	KK	2.9 cd	2.0 c-g	51 fgh
OP54	KK	3.2 cde	2.2 d-h	60 ghi
DM25	NIAB	3.3 cde	2.3 e-h	63 hij
DM28	NIAB	3.5 d-g	2.4 e-h	64 hij
1021-6	NARC	4.0 def	2.7 ghi	65 hij
IR2053	KK	4.3 efg	2.8 hi	68 ijk
1053-1-2 (94)	NARC	4.8 fg	2.9 hi	68 ijk
1021-5	NARC	5.6 gh	2.5 fgh	67 ijk
4048-3	NARC	6.2 h	3.3 ij	72 ijk
50189-8-6	NARC	6.4 h	3.7 j	75 jkl
Bas 385A	NARC	6.5 h	3.7 jk	75 jkl
KS282	KK	6.9 h	4.7 l	78 lm
Bas 385	NIAB	8.4 i	5.2 l	81 lm
4439	NARC	8.8 i	5.5 l	91 m

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly from each other at the 5% level. ^b KK = Kala Shah Kaku; NARC = National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad; NIAB = Nuclear Institute of Agricultural Biology, Faisalabad.

Excess water tolerance

Tolerance of rainfed lowland rice cultivars and breeding lines for submergence at seedling stage

P. P. Singh, A. M. Mazaredo, B. S. Vergara, B. N. Singh, and D. J. Mackill, IRRI

Submergence tolerance is a major trait needed for rice grown in submergence-prone rainfed lowland or tidal wetlands. Native rice cultivars (FR13A, FR43B) have been identified with 12 d submergence tolerance. Other cultivars (Chenab 64-117) have about 7 d submergence tolerance. But those cultivars have low yield potential. New donors and recombinant lines for improved plant type background are needed.

We screened 55 rainfed lowland rices (traditional cultivars and improved lines) in the greenhouse for tolerance for complete submergence. Seedlings were raised in 40- × 25- × 6-cm porcelain trays filled with Maahas clay soil. Ten lines, at 10 seedlings/line were maintained in each tray in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Seedlings were completely submerged 10 d after seeding (DAS) in a 150- × 150- × 45-cm artificial tank. Water depth 30 cm above the soil level, water temperature 30 °C, and light intensity 0.59 watt/m² were maintained, FR13A and IR42 were used as resistant and susceptible checks. Seedling height was measured before submergence (H_1) and after 7 d submergence (H_2). Survival was measured 5 d after the end of submergence (22 DAS). Elongation was calculated as $H_2 - H_1$ for entries with at least 20% survival.

Survival of IR43522-37-3-3 and IR40931-33-1-3-2 compared with that of resistant check FR13A (see table). Ten other lines were moderately resistant (at least 40% survival).